

Thermodynamic Study of Complexation of Some Rare Earth Metal Ions with 3-hydroxynaphthalene-2-carboxylic Acid

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The complexes formed by 3-hydroxy naphthalene-2-carboxylic acid with metal ions like Pr(III), Nd(III), Gd(III), Dy(III), Er(III) and Yb(III) at the temperature range 20-40°, at different ionic strengths in 50% volume percentage dioxane—water medium have been studied by pH-metric method. Thermodynamic fructions have also been evaluated in each case.

THE complexes of 3-hydroxynaphthalene-2-carboxylic acid with different metal ions have been studied by various workers under different experimental conditions¹⁻⁵. Recently complexes of few lanthanides with 3-hydroxynaphthalene-2-carboxylic acid have been prepared in which coordination through oxygen of hydroxyl group of the acid has been indicated⁶. Thermodynamic stability constants and thermodynamic functions of Y(III), Ce(III) and La(III) complexes with the above ligand in aqueous dioxane (50%, v/v) at three temperatures and four different ionic strengths have been reported in our earlier communications^{7,8}.

In the present study, the thermodynamic stability constants of Pr(III), Nd(III), Gd(III), Dy(III), Er(III) and Yb(III) with 3-hydroxynaphthalene-2-carboxylic acid have been determined in 50 vol% dioxane-water medium, at 30° and at various ionic strengths of 0.05M, 0.10M, 0.15M and 0.20M (KNO₃) using Irving Rossotti titration technique⁹.

The results of determination of stability constants and thermodynamic functions of the above lanthanides with the same ligand at 20°, 30° and 40° and 0.1 M (KNO₃) ionic strength have already been reported in our earlier communication¹⁰.

Experimental

All chemicals used were of AnalaR grade. The double-distilled CO₂ free water was used in all experimental work. Dioxane was purified by the recommended procedure¹¹. The solution of the ligand (0.05M) was prepared by dissolving in dioxane. The mole ratio of metal to ligand was kept 1 : 5 in order to fulfil the maximum coordination number of metal ions.

Photovolt digital pH-meter type M-120 (U.S.A.) having an accuracy of ±0.002 unit was used. The titrations were carried out at (30 ± 0.1)°. The design

of the cell was such that it could accommodate a glass stirrer, a micro burette and a glass electrode.

The three solutions (total volume 50 ml in each case) were prepared as follows :

A, 1.0 × 10⁻² M HNO₃; B, 1.0 × 10⁻² M HNO₃ + 5.0 × 10⁻² M ligand; C, 1.0 × 10⁻² M HNO₃ + 5.0 × 10⁻² M ligand + 1.0 × 10⁻² M metal ion solution, such that the concentrations of the common ingredients were identical in different cases. An appropriate quantity of potassium nitrate solution (1.0M) was added to maintain the desired ionic strength, 0.05M, 0.10M, 0.15M, 0.20M. The above solutions were titrated against standard potassium hydroxide solution prepared in aqueous dioxane (50%, v/v).

The concentrations were corrected for the changes in volume produced by the addition of alkali during titrations. The difference in the amount of potassium hydroxide utilised for the last two titrations (B and C) is a measure of the extent of complexation. From the titration curves it is observed that the metal ligand curve is well separated from the ligand titration curve which proves that the liberation of protons is due to chelation.

Results and Discussion

Values of formation functions \bar{n}_A , \bar{n} and pL were calculated using the standard expressions⁹.

The calculations of practical stability constants of proton complexes were done by plotting \bar{n}_A versus pH and then applying various computational methods^{12,13}. The mean values of protonation constants of the ligand at different ionic strengths and one temperature are summarised in Table 1.

TABLE 1—VALUES OF THE PROTONATION CONSTANTS OF THE LIGAND AND CONCENTRATION STABILITY CONSTANTS OF COMPLEXES AT 30°C

Cation	Constants	Method	=0.05M	=0.10M	=0.15M	=0.20M
H(I)	$\log^p K_1^H$		11.30	11.25	11.20	11.15
	$\log^p K_2^H$		2.70	2.65	2.60	2.55
	$\log^p \beta_2^H$		14.00	13.90	13.80	13.70
Pr(III)	$\log K_1$	(i)	8.49	8.30	8.30	8.11
		(ii)	8.49	8.30	8.30	8.11
		(iii)	8.46	8.26	8.22	8.07
		(iv)	8.02	7.96	8.04	7.81
	$\log K_2$	(i)	8.15	7.80	7.65	7.55
		(ii)	8.15	7.80	7.65	7.55
		(iii)	8.04	7.80	7.57	7.43
		(iv)	8.10	7.80	7.48	7.35
	$\log K_3$	(i)	7.90	7.36	7.35	7.25
		(ii)	—	—	—	—
		(iii)	—	—	—	—
		(iv)	8.45	7.73	7.80	7.73
$\log \beta_3$		24.57	23.49	23.32	22.89	
Nd(III)	$\log K_1$	(i)	8.53	8.43	8.30	8.14
		(ii)	8.53	8.43	8.30	8.14
		(iii)	8.51	8.42	8.27	8.08
		(iv)	8.04	8.13	7.98	7.79
	$\log K_2$	(i)	8.23	7.90	7.76	7.65
		(ii)	8.23	7.90	7.76	7.65
		(iii)	8.17	7.80	7.63	7.55
		(iv)	8.25	7.93	7.68	7.55
	$\log K_3$	(i)	7.90	7.35	7.45	7.35
		(ii)	—	—	—	—
		(iii)	—	—	—	—
		(iv)	8.37	7.65	7.90	7.82
$\log \beta_3$		24.66	23.71	23.53	23.16	
Gd(III)	$\log K_1$	(i)	8.63	8.55	8.36	8.36
		(ii)	8.63	8.55	8.36	8.36
		(iii)	8.49	8.41	8.22	8.26
		(iv)	8.20	8.07	7.79	7.79
	$\log K_2$	(i)	8.30	8.30	8.14	8.20
		(ii)	8.30	8.30	8.14	8.20
		(iii)	8.25	8.24	8.09	8.07
		(iv)	8.41	8.53	8.19	8.43
	$\log K_3$	(i)	7.75	7.60	7.85	7.63
		(ii)	—	—	—	—
		(iii)	—	—	—	—
		(iv)	8.07	7.83	8.38	7.95
$\log \beta_3$		24.68	24.43	24.36	24.17	
Dy(III)	$\log K_1$	(i)	8.66	8.58	8.41	8.31
		(ii)	8.66	8.58	8.41	8.13
		(iii)	8.54	8.47	8.41	8.13
		(iv)	8.20	8.13	7.82	7.50
	$\log K_2$	(i)	8.40	8.29	8.26	8.19
		(ii)	8.40	8.29	8.26	8.19
		(iii)	8.32	8.28	8.29	8.15
		(iv)	8.63	8.46	8.45	8.29
	$\log K_3$	(i)	7.70	7.67	7.80	7.95
		(ii)	—	—	—	—
		(iii)	—	—	—	—
		(iv)	7.94	7.94	8.91	8.59
$\log \beta_3$		24.77	24.53	24.48	24.38	
Er(III)	$\log K_1$	(i)	8.93	8.68	8.58	8.49
		(ii)	8.93	8.68	8.58	8.49
		(iii)	8.50	8.12	8.06	7.91
	$\log K_2$	(i)	8.65	8.49	8.36	8.30
		(ii)	8.65	8.49	8.36	8.30
		(iii)	8.64	8.44	8.38	8.21
		(iv)	8.89	8.78	8.53	8.45
	$\log K_3$	(i)	7.88	7.72	7.85	7.78
		(ii)	—	—	—	—
		(iii)	—	—	—	—
	$\log \beta_3$		8.08	7.93	8.20	8.15
			25.17	24.83	24.79	24.51

(Table 1 Contd.)

Yb(III) $\log K_1$	(i)	8.00	8.75	8.70	8.59
	(ii)	9.00	8.75	8.70	8.59
	(iii)	8.86	8.61	8.39	8.44
	(iv)	8.48	8.10	7.85	7.82
$\log K_2$	(i)	8.80	8.63	8.58	8.46
	(ii)	8.80	8.63	8.58	8.34
	(iii)	8.84	8.62	8.56	8.34
	(iv)	9.08	8.76	8.67	8.43
$\log K_3$	(i)	8.11	8.32	8.40	8.29
	(ii)	—	—	—	—
	(iii)	—	—	—	—
	(iv)	8.35	8.86	9.11	9.02
$\log \beta_3$		25.91	25.72	25.63	25.27

(i) Bjerrum's half integral method ;

(ii) Graphical method ;

(iii) Interpolation at various \bar{n} values ;

(iv) Method of successive approximations.

The metal-ligand stability constants have been obtained by analysis of the formation curves obtained by plotting \bar{n} versus pL . These plots indicate that the values of \bar{n} obtained are of the order of 3 for all the metal ions under study at an approximate pH 6.5, above which the hydrolysis region of the rare earth metal ion starts. Bjerrum's half integral method¹³, interpolation at various \bar{n} values, graphical method¹³ and extended to dioxane-water mixture by Van Ujtert and Haas¹⁴ were used to calculate $\log K_1$, $\log K_2$ and $\log K_3$. Since the ratio of successive constants is less than 10^4 , the method of successive approximations¹⁵ was used to refine the values of stability constants obtained by Bjerrum's half integral method. The values of stepwise stability constants obtained by various methods and of overall stability constants obtained by the method of successive approximations have been reported in Table 1. The error limits are ± 0.05 for $\log K$ values.

The small difference between successive constants suggest that the formation of three types of complexes ML_1 , ML_2 and ML_3 proceed simultaneously and may be attributed to the smaller steric hindrance offered by the 3-hydroxynaphthalene-2-carboxylic acid as compared with coordinated water molecule.

The order of overall stability $\log \beta_3$ is $Yb > Er > Dy > Gd > Nd > Pr$. It shows that stability constants increase with decreasing ionic radii, as expected on the basis of regular decrease in ionic radii from La^{3+} to Lu^{3+} .

The metal-ligand stability data at various values (Table 1) reveal that $\log \beta_3$ values decrease with an increase in the ionic strength of the medium. According to Huckel¹⁶, the activity of the metal ion for its interaction with other molecular species varies in inverse proportion to the ionic strength of the medium. On this basis, the decrease in stability for 3-hydroxynaphthalene-2-carboxylic acid complexes with the lanthanons under study in solution of increasing ionic strength is justified.

TABLE 2—VALUES OF THERMODYNAMIC STABILITY CONSTANTS AND FREE ENERGIES AT 30°C

	Metal ions					
	Pr(III)	Nd(III)	Gd(III)	Dy(III)	Er(III)	Yb(III)
log $K_1^{\mu=0}$	8.10	8.11	8.34	8.43	8.70	8.70
log $K_2^{\mu=0}$	8.35	8.48	8.40	8.73	9.04	9.30
log $K_3^{\mu=0}$	8.67	8.56	8.12	7.74	8.04	8.13
Calcd. log $K^{\mu=0}$	25.12	25.15	24.86	24.90	25.78	26.13
Exptl. log $K^{\mu=0}$	25.12	25.15	24.86	24.90	25.78	26.13
ΔF_1 (K cal mole ⁻¹)	-11.23	-11.24	-11.56	-11.68	-12.06	-12.06
ΔF_2 (K cal mole ⁻¹)	-11.57	-11.75	-11.64	-12.10	-12.53	-12.89
ΔF_3 (K cal mole ⁻¹)	-12.02	-11.86	-11.25	-10.73	-11.14	-11.27
Calcd. ΔF (K cal mole ⁻¹)	-34.82	-34.86	-34.45	-34.51	-35.73	-36.22
Exptl. ΔF (K cal mole ⁻¹)	-34.82	-34.86	-34.45	-34.51	-35.73	-36.22

The values of log step stability constants at various ionic strengths, extrapolated to zero ionic strength gave step thermodynamic stability constant¹⁷. These values are shown in Table 2 as log $K_1^{\mu=0}$, log $K_2^{\mu=0}$, log $K_3^{\mu=0}$. Their sum is shown as calculated log $K^{\mu=0}$. The values of overall stability constant log β_3 at various ionic strengths were likewise extrapolated to zero ionic strengths and the overall thermodynamic stability constants thus obtained have been symbolised as experimental log $K^{\mu=0}$.

Ligational standard free energy was obtained from the expression :

$$\Delta F = -2.303 RT \log K^{\mu=0}$$

The precision of ΔF value is $\pm 0.08K$ cal mole⁻¹.

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